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STATISTICAL ASSESSMENT OF CONSOLIDATION PROCESSES IN THE BANKING SYSTEM

The rationalisation of the market economy and the banking system implies its transformation and consolidation, taking into account the principles of market self-organisation of banking institutions. In order to study the development of consolidation processes in the banking industry, we believe it is advisable to identify the necessary statistical indicators that allow us to assess the degree and speed of bank concentration as a result of corporate consolidation:

- indicators of market (industry) concentration: concentration ratio (CR), Herfindahl-Hirschman index (HHI), ranked concentration index (Hoff-Tydmann index, Rosenbluth index);

- indicators of inequality (unevenness) in the distribution of market shares of its participants: Gini coefficient, Atkinson index, entropy index, Theil coefficient, coefficient of variation, etc.

Let us consider in more detail the essence and procedure for determining concentration indicators in order to identify the most appropriate ones for assessing the degree of concentration and consolidation of the Ukrainian banking sector.

The concentration ratio (CR) shows what share of the market is held by the largest market participants and is defined as follows [1]:

$$CR3 = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + \dots + S_n, \quad (1)$$

where $S_1, S_2, S_3 \dots S_n$ - are the market shares in terms of assets of the n largest banks;

In the world financial practice, the most popular concentration ratios are CR3, CR4, CR5, CR10, CR15. It is also possible to calculate the inverse of CR, which shows the number of banks that account for a given percentage of the market share. These concentration ratios allow to determine and take into account the concentration of the banking services market only by the largest banks, while ignoring the performance of small and medium-sized banks.

The Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI) is the basis for determining other market concentration indicators; it is considered a full information index because it takes into account the specifics of the distribution of market participants by their size. The HHI is the sum of the squared shares of all banks in a given market and is calculated using the following formula:

$$HHI = S_1 + S_2 + S_3 + \dots + S_n = \sum_{i=1}^n (S_i)^2, \quad (2)$$

where $S_1, S_2, S_3, \dots S_n$ - are the squares of the banks' market shares.

This index emphasises the importance of the largest institutional unit in the total; the higher the value of the index, the higher the level of concentration. The value of this index increases with the growth of market monopolisation and, conversely, decreases with the reduction of concentration in a competitive market. The minimum value of the Herfindahl-Hirschman Index (HHI_{min}) is reached when banks have the same market share, as defined by the following formula [1]:

$$HHI_{min} = 10000 / N, \quad (3)$$

where N - is the total number of banks.

The NIM and the concentration ratio (CR) are the basis for economic entities to make decisions on consolidation, as well as the basic basis for characterising the market in terms of its concentration. In global practice, all markets are divided into three groups depending on concentration indicators (concentration ratio (CR3) and the HHI index) [2]:

- 1) weakly concentrated industries with $CR3 < 45\%$ and $HHI < 1000$;
- 2) markets with moderate concentration: $45\% < CR3 < 70\%$, $1000 < HHI < 2000$;
- 3) highly concentrated industries for which $70\% < CR3 < 100\%$, $2000 < HHI < 10,000$.

At present, the Ukrainian legal framework does not set forth the meaning of the above concentration indicators, but analysts and researchers use them in their calculations and computations.

The Gini Coefficient (GC) is an indicator of the uneven distribution of banks; it reproduces the information contained in the Lorenz curve, which is the difference between the actual distribution of a variable and the hypothetical state in which this value has a uniform distribution. In this hypothetical state, all banks would be in an equal position (absolute equality of banks in the market) and the value of the GC index would be zero. The maximum value of the Gini coefficient is one and indicates absolute inequality - when one largest bank owns all the assets of the banking sector. The Gini coefficient is defined as follows [2]:

$$GC = \sum_{i=1}^N 2 * (X_i - Y_i) * \Delta X_i, \quad (4)$$

where X_i - is the share of banks ranked by asset growth: $X_i = \frac{i}{N} * 100\%$;

Y_i - is the cumulative share of banks ranked by asset growth.

ΔX_i - is the deviation in the share of the number of banks in the reporting period:

$$\Delta X_i = X_i - X_{i-1};$$

The Atkinson Index (AI) is an indicator of inequality and allows to measure the shift in the distribution among the smallest market participants. This indicator can be transformed into a normative one by introducing a sensitivity parameter (ε), which can be changed from zero to infinity to focus on the specifics of the distribution of small market participants.

The Generalised Entropy index (GE) is also an inequality indicator that contains a specified sensitivity component (ε), an increase in which increases the sensitivity of GE (ε) to uneven distribution among the largest banks. The concept of «entropy» was first introduced by Clausius in thermodynamics in 1865 to define the irreversibility of energy dissipation. In essence, entropy makes it possible to measure the deviation of a real-world process from its ideal state. The entropy index is defined as the sum of the products of the shares of banks in the market and the natural logarithms of their inverse values [3]:

$$GE = \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i * \ln(1/X_i)), \quad (5)$$

where X_i - is the market share of banks ranked by asset growth;

N - total number of banks;

\ln - is the natural logarithm of $(1/x_i)$.

The entropy index measures the disorderly distribution of shares among market participants and is inversely related to the level of market concentration: the higher the entropy index, the lower the concentration of market participants and the higher the degree of uniformity of market shares, and vice versa, the higher the entropy index, the less ability market participants have to influence the market price.

Variation coefficient is the ratio of the standard deviation of bank assets to the arithmetic mean of the distribution of bank assets:

$$K_{VAR} = \frac{\sigma(x)}{\bar{x}} * 100\%, \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma(x)$ - is the standard deviation of bank assets,

\bar{x} - is the arithmetic mean of the distribution of banking assets.

It is worth noting that the main essence of these indicators is to reflect the market share and the inequality of distribution of these shares for market participants (industry). According to researchers, an ideal concentration indicator should meet the following requirements [3]:

- calculation of the indicator not for n firms in the market, but for k firms ranked in descending order of market share with $k < n$;

- increase in the concentration indicator if the share of a large firm increases at the expense of a small firm;

- a decrease in the level of concentration when a new firm enters the market;
- an increase in the degree of market concentration in the event of mergers and acquisitions.

Of the concentration indicators mentioned above, the concentration ratio and the Herfindahl-Hirschman index meet these requirements to the greatest extent, while other indicators (Gini coefficient, variation, dispersion) partially meet these conditions (they do not take into account the number of banks in the market), so they can be considered additional rather than full-fledged measures of banking sector concentration. However, it is also worth noting that changes in the heterogeneity of the banking sector's market structure make it possible to understand the reasons for the growth or decline in concentration. Therefore, the key indicators for assessing the state of consolidation of the banking sector in our study will be the concentration ratio (CR3), the Herfindahl-Hirschman index (HHI), and the entropy coefficient (GE).

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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA (2023-2025): PROGRESS, POLICIES AND APPLICATIONS

This article examines and critically analyzes recent developments in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) in the Republic of Moldova over the past two to three years. It highlights technological advancements, public policy initiatives, and the practical implementation of AI in education, public administration, and the business sector. The study investigates strategic governmental actions, collaborations with international organizations, and the broader impact on both the educational landscape and the economic environment. It also addresses key challenges related to digital